

CONCEPT OF LEGAL AWARENESS AND HUMAN RIGHTS

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Annotation: This article analyzes the issues of ensuring human rights and freedoms and the formation of mechanisms for their protection in the process of establishing a democratic legal state in Uzbekistan. It also covers the process of implementing international legal standards in national legislation of Uzbekistan, its activities within the framework of UN conventions, and the practical significance of the right to development.

Keywords: Human rights, freedom, democratic state, civil society, UN convention, right to development.

One of the main conditions for building a democratic legal state in Uzbekistan is to promote the protection of fundamental rights and freedoms of the individual and create a system of practical guarantees of the rights of every person in society. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov noted, "we will not abandon the goal we have set for ourselves of building a democratic state and civil society, we will not deviate from the path of building a free, prosperous life for every person living on our sacred land, where no one and nothing is inferior." In its foreign and domestic policy, the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on the principle that "human rights are indisputably universal, and their protection is a legitimate need of the relevant states," as affirmed at the Second World Conference on Human Rights of the United Nations in 1993. In our country, targeted work is being carried out to ensure human rights and freedoms, a whole system of legislative acts has been developed, and national institutions for the protection of human rights and freedoms are successfully operating. After the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence, the first international legal instrument to which it acceded was the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. This expresses the true goals of Uzbekistan in the development, protection and guarantee of human rights. Today, the Republic has ratified more than 70 international legal instruments on human rights and freedoms. With the accession of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the main instruments on human rights and freedoms, the basic universally recognized principles of international law are gradually being implemented into the national legal system.

The mechanism of reports on UN convention documents plays an important role in the implementation of international legal instruments in the field of human rights. 2011 1 Karimov I.A. Towards overcoming the consequences of the global

crisis, modernization of our country and advancement to the level of developed countries. National reports on the main documents of the UN to which the Republic of Uzbekistan has acceded were submitted and considered in the relevant committees of the Organization on the main documents on human rights and freedoms, including the "Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women"; "Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination"; "Convention on the Rights of the Child", "Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment", "International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights"; Reports have been submitted on the documents of the "International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights". It is worth noting that the process of implementing international legal standards into the national legislation of Uzbekistan is becoming stable, systematic and irreversible.

As a result of this event, a number of laws and by-laws are being reviewed for compliance with the requirements of generally recognized principles and norms of international law. Naturally, the development and adoption of plans in this or that area does not yet mean the solution of the problem, but the identification of strategic priorities and the full implementation of the tasks set are the solution to the problem. The international community is now paying special attention to the right to development. This right is inherent in peoples and man and is part of the fundamental human rights. This right was finally enshrined in the Declaration on the Right to Development, adopted by the UN General Assembly in 1986. This Declaration states that: development is comprehensive economic, cultural, social and political progress, aimed at ensuring the equal and fair enjoyment of the benefits created by it by all persons participating in it and their active participation in it. As noted, a person is the main subject of the development process and must be an active participant in the right to development. The experience of most democratic countries shows that it is impossible to establish a civil society and a legal state without creating an effective mechanism for ensuring and protecting human rights, and especially the rights and freedoms of the "first generation", at the national level. The practical provision of individual rights and freedoms is the basis for the stable and consistent development of each state. Therefore, the study of the modern concept of human rights, the study of issues related to the history and theory of the problem is an important and urgent issue for Uzbek legal science. Before proceeding to the study of the subject "General Theory of Human Rights", it is necessary to clarify the subject, goals and objectives of this discipline.

In conclusion, in the process of building a democratic legal state in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the issue of ensuring human rights and freedoms is one of the priority areas of state policy. Over the years of independence, our country has consistently implemented the basic principles and norms of international law into its national legislation, forming a solid legal framework aimed at protecting human interests. Uzbekistan's accession to UN conventions and other international documents, as well as regular reporting on their implementation, demonstrate political will and openness in this regard. The activities of national human rights institutions, as well as the implementation of concepts such as the "Right to Development", serve to strengthen the principles of justice, equality and sustainable development in society. Therefore, ensuring human rights and freedoms in practice is one of the most important factors in the development of civil society and strengthening democratic values in Uzbekistan

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